

Special Relativity and Built-In Wave Solution Part 2

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In Part 1, we focused on the wave equation $E=pc$ ($c=\text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$ hence $\Delta t = \hbar / E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$) which follows from $EE = ppcc + m_0m_0cccc$ ((1)) with $m_0=0$. We obtained this equation from considerations of Newtonian mechanics, in particular: $KE=.5mv^2$ and $p=mv$. Here, we only consider the case of $m_0>0$, but note that it requires the presence of a speed c which is the same in all frames and is an upper bound speed. In Part I, we noted that from a Newtonian point of view, even though ((1)) exists, suggesting a Lorentz transformation for E and p does not mean that x,ct transform in the same way. They may represent absolute space-time as in the Newtonian view. We first show that this contradicts ((1)) indicating that E and pc are interconnected with space time. This allows one to write the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px = \text{constant}$ ((2)) from ((1)). We note that $v = pc/E$, but if one considers ((2)) and arbitrarily introduces $\Delta t = \text{constant} / E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant} / p$, then $\Delta x / \Delta t = cc/v$, i.e. is greater than c . The point we make is that one has a right angle triangle with $\Delta x / \Delta t$ on the hypotenuse and c on the adjacent, meaning that regardless of E and p , one always has the same c value on the adjacent indicating it is a frame independent value. To interpret this result physically, we suggest that Δx and Δt may be ranges involved in an interaction and c the maximum speed associated with an interaction. Thus, the quantum notions of Δx and Δt may possibly be seen to emerge without directly invoking the wave nature of a photon, which was the main feature/argument of Part 1.

$EE = ppcc + m_0m_0cccc$

In Part I, we argued for the existence of ((1)) based on complementarity of two frames moving at a relative speed of $-v$ with respect to each other. Each frame thinks it is at rest and the other is moving. Thus, we argue that there must exist an equation linking m_0 (rest) and m , $KE=.5mv^2$ and $p=mv$. This requires:

$(m_0 D + .5mv^2) (m_0D+.5mv^2) - mv^2mv \text{ approx} = m_0m_0 DD$ ((3))

More generally, one has $(p=0, m_0D)$ transforming to a $(p \text{ sqrt}(D), E)$ via:

$| g(v) \quad vg(v) |$ ((4))
 $|vg(v) \quad g(v) |$

Using ((3)) as a guide, one finds that: $g(v) = 1/\text{sqrt}(1-vv/cc)$ ((5))

c is a constant speed in all frames and seems to be an upper bound. One then has:

$EE = ppcc + m_0m_0cccc$ ((6))

Instead of setting $m_0=0$ and using $E=pc$ as a wave-equation for a photon, we ask: Does ((6)) have any implications on space-time, i.e. x,t ? In Newtonian mechanics, one would postulate:

$$x' = x + vt \quad \text{and} \quad t' = t \quad ((7)) \quad (\text{i.e. absolute spacetime})$$

This is equivalent to ((4)) with $g(v)=1$. In other words, there would be two different transformations, one for E,p (which are linked with work done on a rest particle m_0) and one for x,t , which are supposedly fixed as they measure a kind of absolute space-time in Newtonian mechanics. The problem with this view is that it contradicts ((6)) because p and E for $m_0>0$ are ultimately linked to v which, in turn, is linked to space time. In particular, consider:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((8))$$

If one postulates that one has $x=0, t$ in a rest frame and $x'=vgt$ and $t'=gt$ in a moving frame (instead of ((7))) then, this leads to (for $c=1$)

$$X'x' - t't' = tt \rightarrow m_0 m_0 g g v v - g g m_0 m_0 = m_0 m_0 \quad \text{or} \quad ((1)) \quad ((9))$$

Thus, having x,ct transformation like pc,E leads to ((9)) being equivalent to ((1)), while ((7)) does not. ((7)) (the Newtonian view) does not seem to be consistent with the complementarity of moving frames. As a result, space-time (x,t) also transforms like pc, E and is linked with time dilation and length contraction as is well-known.

The point we wish to make here, is that one may create a hybrid Lorentz invariant (which we have used in previous notes):

$$\text{Constant} = -Et + px \quad (\text{classical action both relativistic and nonrelativistic if } v=x/t) \quad ((10))$$

It is known that: $v = pc/E$ and this is the dynamic speed of the moving rest mass. One may arbitrarily define from ((10)):

$$\Delta t = \text{constant}/E \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta p = \text{constant} \times x \quad ((11))$$

The question becomes: How is this arbitrary definition ((11)) linked with any physical reality? We note that:

$$\Delta x / \Delta t = cc/v \quad ((12)) \quad cc/v > c$$

((12)) cannot be a physical energy carrying speed because it is larger than c , but it does not need to be associated with a physical speed, but rather with interaction intervals. We first note that one may write a right angle triangle with:

$$\Delta x / \Delta t \text{ on the hypotenuse and } c \text{ on the adjacent} \quad ((12))$$

This, we argue, shows that one always has c on the adjacent regardless of E and p so c is a constant viewed from all frames. We suggest one might argue that Δx and Δt are intervals linked with an interaction which are associated with the notion that the maximum speed that may possibly be involved in the interaction is c . We note that in textbooks describing an accelerating charge, signals traveling at the speed c are sometimes shown as existing and these are said to mediate the changes at the center-of-mass point with the field at some distance away. (This approach of signals moving at c i.e the idea of a retarded time is equivalent to special relativity.) We suggest that the Δx and Δt defined above allow for the notion of such c signals which are the same in any frame as the adjacent (of the right angle triangle) always yields the same value c . We suggest one now has the notion of two “new” Δx and Δt intervals associated with an interaction (E, p) and these are the intervals of quantum mechanics.

We have argued in previous notes that if one has a photon moving with momentum p , it may interfere with a 2-slit apparatus at rest as long as the slit separation is about \hbar/p . If the 2-slit apparatus moves at constant speed, then one may go into the rest frame of the 2-slit apparatus and the slit separation is \hbar/p' . Thus, the interaction is key and is linked to the Δx and Δt even though c is the same regardless of the frame. This seems to be consistent with the idea of Δx and Δt being interaction intervals. Furthermore in a 2-slit experiment, one does not need to worry about Δt intervals as spatial considerations suffice for solving the problem. This again suggests that one consider Δx and Δt as interaction intervals.

We suggest that this is a possible approach to introducing the quantum Δx , Δt without invoking the notion of a photon as a physical self-wave (as done in Part 1) and then arguing that the frequency and wavelength features of E and p should carryover to a particle with rest mass.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part 1, we obtained $E = pc + m_0 c^2$ from Newtonian concepts of $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $p = mv$. We then set $m_0 = 0$ and argued that $E = pc$ is equivalent to a wave-equation: $\text{speed} = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$ allowing one to associate E with a physical frequency and p , a physical wavelength. We then tried to apply this idea to E and p to a particle with rest mass.

Here, we acknowledge that a particle with rest mass has $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$, i.e. an upper bound speed c appears which is the same in all frames, but we avoid associating c with a wave. Instead, we show that ((1)) is consistent with x, ct transforming in the same manner as pc, E and not according to Newtonian mechanics, i.e. $t' = t$, $x' = x + vt$. We then argue that this allows one to write the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + px = \text{constant}$. We arbitrarily introduce $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$ and write $\Delta x / \Delta t = cc/v$. This is a fictitious speed, but represents the hypotenuse of a right-angle triangle such that the adjacent is always c , regardless of E, p , i.e of the frame. We suggest that one may interpret Δx and Δt as representing intervals associated with an interaction such that the maximum interaction speed is c , which is the same in all frames. In this way, we suggest that the quantum $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ intervals emerge from the consideration of a particle with rest mass, without having to invoke the wave nature of a photon as was done in Part 1.

